

FAIR Data Hub - User Journeys

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Version 1.0 – November 2024

Before reading the 'journeys', it is important to keep in mind that adaptability of the FDH is on the foreground allowing to implement institutional policies and discipline-specific requirements. For instance, the FDH will be able to support various more specific metadata schemes in addition to standard solutions.

Journey 1A: Archiving via upload suitable for smaller data packages (< 10 GB)

In short:

The researcher stores data in his/ her workspace, for instance laptop/ pc or other specific local storage during the research project. The FDH enables the researcher to archive data stored in the workspace after data collection, certain processing steps and/or at the end of a research experiment/ project.

Start of journey.

Steps (see figure 1 on next page for corresponding workflow):

1. The researcher prepares a data package for archiving in his/ her own workspace (not provided by the FDH), optional with assistance or advice from a data steward or other support. A data package to be archived contains for example: raw data, processed data, data descriptions (metadata) including syntax and dictionaries (e.g., codebooks), retention period declarations, informed consent forms and agreements when applicable, etc. The faculty/ research institute provides the guidelines for the content of a data package based on their local policies.
2. The researcher opens the FDH web page (e.g., datahub.uva.nl), logs in with his/ her UvA credentials, and deposits a data package (< 10 GB) by using the option: '**ready for uploading**'. Next, the FDH presents the project titles (and other identifiers) registered by the researcher in Research Management Services (RMS: rms.uva.nl). The researcher selects the project that belongs to the data package. If **no projects** are registered in RMS and therefore, can't be shown in FDH, the researcher provides a project title. Finally, the researcher selects the data package to upload. The researcher can modify the name of the (compressed) folder containing the data package and a version number will be automatically added to the name. In this journey, the FDH serves as a 'gateway' for data packages to be archived, which means that after the upload, the FDH saves the data package on 'intermediate' storage. This allows the data steward to manage and check (i.e., quality control) the data package for archiving. However, the faculty/ research institute determines whether checks by data stewards and/or other support is part of the procedure.

The upload of a data package to the FDH triggers the following automations:

- a. Ingesting relevant metadata from sources (if available) such as Research Management Services (RMS: rms.uva.nl) and storing them structurally in the FDH metadata repository. If metadata already exist for the project in the FDH, the latest version of the metadata will be presented to the researcher, which can be modified and saved as a new version.
- b. If **a check** of the data package is part of the procedure, labelling the data package as '**check before archiving**' and notifying the 'assigned' data steward. After FDH login, the data steward gets an overview (list) of the prepared data package(s) 'Waiting to Check' and can also view the related metadata template (see step 3).
- c. If **no check** of the data package is part of the procedure, labelling the data package as '**ready for archiving**'.

Workflow:

Figure 1. (Meta)Data Archivation via Upload.

Note:

- I. Researchers of the UvA faculties make use of RMS to register research projects and related content concerning data management, data protection, and ethics (FNWI for now only for ethical concerns). These registrations contain research related metadata. One of the FDH goals is to connect RMS as source for metadata extraction. However, also other sources could be connected when feasible. For instance, extraction of metadata stored in data collection systems (e.g., measuring instruments) or logging systems such as an electronic lab notebook (ELN). Automatic extractions are preferred, but a second-best option could be through imports of standard data exchange formats such as JSON and XML files when sources are able to provide these files straightforwardly.
 - II. The faculty/ research institute determines the procedure for checking the data package before archiving. This could range from no checks at all, some basic automated checks if the structure of the data package allows this, but probably not available in the initial version of the FDH, to more extensive manual checks by the data steward.
3. The FDH:
 - a. First, automatically checks the ingested and stored metadata. If **no metadata** can be ingested an empty template will appear in step 3b.
 - b. Second, shows the researcher the stored metadata in a template and conveys when crucial metadata for archiving are missing or invalid in the template.
 4. The researcher completes the relevant metadata in the template for archiving. The researcher can request support from and communicates with data stewards at the faculty or metadata/ RDM specialists at the library using an integrated messaging/ mailing system to finalize the metadata. The minimal set of pre-defined metadata is required, which is needed for adequate archiving. Nonetheless, storing additional metadata is possible and further refinement of these metadata can be done in time with the help of the faculties. The status ('not ready'/'ready') of the metadata for archiving will be visible in the FDH for the researcher as well as the data steward.
 5. If the faculty/ research institute guidelines:
 - a. **Don't instruct** manual checks (or automated checks have been resolved) and if the **metadata is 'ready'** (see step 4), the FDH automatically transfers the data package from the 'intermediate' storage to the 'long-term' archive, after which the data package becomes 'read only'. The researcher and data steward are notified of this (meta)data import. After archiving, the data package is automatically deleted (after a predefined period) from the 'intermediate' storage.
 - b. **Do instruct** manual checks, the data steward checks the data package on the 'intermediate' storage of the FDH. For instance, whether the data provenance¹ is sufficient. The data steward can interact with the researcher and/or other support by means of the integrated messaging system in the FDH to provide or receive support/ advice to complete the data package for archiving.
 6. If the data steward considers the data package:
 - a. As **'not ready'** the researcher reworks the data package on his/her workspace, possibly in collaboration with data steward or other support. For collaboration, the data steward and/or other support must be authorised to access the data package in a shared environment. Thereafter, the researcher uploads the reworked version of the data package. The status of the data package will change to 'updated', requesting the data steward for another check.

¹ Full provenance consists of two aspects: (1) Descriptions of data origin and collection including instruments and persons involved and for which purpose; (2) Descriptions of processing steps to get from the collected data to the final results.

- b. As **'ready'** the data steward labels the data package as **'ready for archiving'** in the FDH. Next, if also the **metadata is 'ready'** (see step 4), the data package will be transferred automatically to the 'long-term' archive, after which it becomes 'read only'. The researcher and data steward are notified of this (meta)data import. After archiving, the data package is automatically deleted (after a predefined period) from the 'intermediate' storage and its status in the FDH changes to **'archived'**.

End of journey.

Note:

- I. Retention period: The data package remains in the archive at least as long as the registered retention period, which is stored as required metadata in the FDH. When the retention period has expired, there are two options:
 - a. The researcher and data steward are notified (if unavailable their substitutes and/or institute director) and after a pre-defined period the data package is automatically removed from the 'long-term' archive.
 - b. The researcher and data steward are notified (if unavailable their substitutes and/or institute director), and the data package is only removed from 'long-term' archive after a confirmation process involving the researcher/substitute and/or the institute director (to be decided).
- II. Data package retrieval:
 - a. The researcher who is responsible for the research project is permitted to download a copy of the data package from the archive to their workspace via the FDH. However, changes to a data package will always be archived as a new version and require to go through the described steps above.
 - b. Researchers not involved in the research project are unable to view or retrieve data packages from the archive. This will always involve an 'request' and 'approval' procedure.

Journey 1B: Archiving via direct transfer suitable for bigger data packages (> 10 GB) and when using generic solutions as workspace to prepare data packages

In short:

The researcher stores data in his/ her workspace containing institute/ faculty storage or cloud solutions such as OneDrive, Research Drive, VRE during the research project. The FDH enables the researcher to archive data stored in the workspace after data collection, certain processing steps and/or at the end of a research experiment/ project.

Start of journey.

Steps (see figure 2 on next page for corresponding workflow):

1. The researcher prepares a data package for archiving in his/ her own workspace (not provided by the FDH), optional with assistance or advice from a data steward or other support. A data package to be archived contains for example: raw data, processed data, data descriptions (metadata) including syntax and dictionaries (e.g., codebooks), retention period declarations, informed consent forms and agreements when applicable, etc. The faculty/ research institute provides the guidelines for the content of a data package based on their local policies.
2. The researcher opens the FDH web page (e.g., datahub.uva.nl), logs in with his/ her Uva credentials and selects the option: **'ready for transferring'**. This indicates that a data package has been prepared for deposit on the storage solution (size often > 10 GB) of the faculty/ research institute or on a common cloud solution such as OneDrive, Research Drive, or VRE. Next, the FDH presents the project titles (and other identifiers) registered by the researcher in Research Management Services (RMS: rms.uva.nl). The researcher selects the

Workflow:

Figure 2. (Meta)Data Archivation via Direct Transfer.

project that belongs to the data package to archive. If **no projects** are registered in RMS and therefore, can't be shown in FDH, the researcher provides a project title related to the data package. Finally, the researcher provides the name of the data package. This name with a version number will be given to the (compressed) folder containing the data package in the archive.

In this journey, interfacing directly with the 'long-term' archive for the data package transfer is most optimal. This means that **no intermediate storage** is available for the data steward to check the data package. Therefore, checks should take place on the same storage system on which the data package has been prepared. However, the faculty/ research institute determines whether checks by data stewards and/or other support is part of the procedure.

Although in this case, the FDH does not store the data package temporarily to perform (automatic) checks, it still handles the import, validation, and completion of the 'metadata'. Selecting the option '**ready for transferring**' in the FDH triggers the following automations:

- a. Ingesting relevant metadata from sources (if available) such as Research Management Services (RMS: rms.uva.nl) and storing them structurally in the FDH repository. If metadata already exist for the project in the FDH, the latest version of the metadata will be presented to the researcher, which can be modified and saved as a new version.
- b. If a **check** of the data package is part of the procedure, labelling the data package as '**check before archiving**' and notifying the 'assigned' data steward. After FDH login, the data steward gets an overview (list) of the prepared data package(s) 'Waiting to Check' and can view the related metadata template (see step 3). However, in this case the data packages are not available on the 'intermediate' storage but only on the storage solution of the faculty/ research institute or a cloud solution such as OneDrive, Research Drive, or VRE.
- c. If **no check** of the data package is part of the procedure, labelling the data package as '**ready for archiving**'.

Note:

- I. Researchers of the UvA faculties make use of RMS to register research projects and related content concerning data management, data protection, and ethics (FNWI for now only for ethical concerns). These registrations contain research related metadata. One of the FDH goals is to connect RMS as source for metadata extraction. However, also other sources could be connected when feasible. For instance, extraction of metadata stored in data collection systems (e.g., measuring instruments) or logging systems such as an electronic lab notebook (ELN). Automatic extractions are preferred, but a second-best option could be through imports of standard data exchange formats such as JSON and XML files when sources are able to provide these files straightforwardly.
 - II. The faculty/ research institute determines the procedure for checking the data package before archiving. This could range from no checks at all, some basic automated checks if the structure of the data package allows this but probably not available in the initial version of the FDH, to more extensive manual checks by the data steward.
3. The FDH:
- a. First, automatically checks the ingested and stored metadata. If **no metadata** can be ingested an empty template will appear in step 3b.
 - b. Second, shows the researcher not only the stored metadata in a template but also conveys when crucial metadata for archiving are missing or invalid.
4. The researcher completes the relevant metadata in the template for archiving. The researcher can request support from and communicates with data stewards at the faculty or metadata/ RDM specialists at the library using an integrated messaging/ mailing system to finalize the metadata. The minimal set of pre-defined metadata is required, which is needed for adequate archiving. Nonetheless, storing additional metadata is possible and further

refinement of these metadata can be done in time with the help of the faculties. The status ('ready'/'not ready') of the metadata for archiving will be visible in the FDH for the researcher as well as the data steward.

5. If the faculty/ research institute guidelines:
 - a. **Don't instruct** manual checks (or automated checks have been resolved) and the **metadata is 'ready'** (see step 4), the FDH initiates automatic transfer of the data package to the 'long-term' archive, after which the data package becomes 'read only'. The researcher, data steward and system administrator of the workspace (i.e., the system on which the data package has been prepared) are notified of this (meta)data import. This could be the trigger to (automatically) remove (after a predefined period) the data package from the workspace storage.
 - b. **Do instruct** manual checks, the data steward checks the data package in the 'workspace', i.e., the system on which the data package has been prepared. For instance, whether the data provenance² is sufficient. Therefore, the data steward must be authorised to access the workspace. The data steward can interact with the researcher and/or other support by means of the integrated messaging system in the FDH to provide or receive support/ advice to complete the data package for archiving.
6. If the data steward considers the data package:
 - c. As **'not ready'**, the researcher accesses the workspace (i.e., the system on which the data package has been prepared) to rework the data package for archiving. Possibly in collaboration, but then collaborators (i.e., data steward, other support) should be authorized to access and edit the data package on the workspace. Thereafter, the researcher marks the 'reworked' version of the data package as 'updated' requesting the data steward for another check.
 - a. As **'ready'**, the data steward labels the data package as **'ready for archiving'** in the FDH. Next, if also the **metadata is 'ready'** (see step 4), the data package will be transferred automatically to the 'long-term' archive, after which it becomes 'read only' and its status in the FDH changes to **'archived'**. The researcher, data steward, and system administrator of the workspace (i.e., the system on which the data package has been prepared) are notified of this (meta)data import. This could be the trigger to (automatically) remove (after a predefined period) the data package from the workspace storage.

End of journey.

Note:

- I. Retention period: The data package remains in the archive at least as long as the registered retention period, which is stored as required metadata in the FDH. When the retention period has expired, there are two options:
 - a. The researcher and data steward are notified (if unavailable their substitutes and/or institute director) and after a pre-defined period the data package is automatically removed from the 'long-term' archive.
 - b. The researcher and data steward are notified (if unavailable their substitutes and/or institute director), and the data package is only removed from 'long-term' archive after a confirmation process involving the researcher/substitute and/or the institute director (to be decided).
- II. Data package retrieval:
 - a. The researcher who is responsible for the research project is permitted to download a copy of the data package from the archive to their workspace via the FDH. However,

² Full provenance consists of two aspects: (1) Descriptions of data origin and collection including instruments and persons involved and for which purpose; (2) Descriptions of processing steps to get from the collected data to the final results.

changes to a data package will always be archived as a new version and require to go through the described steps above.

- b. Researchers not involved in the research project are unable to view or retrieve data packages from the archive. This will always involve an ‘request’ and ‘approval’ procedure.

Journey 2: Data Publication

In short:

The researcher stores data in his/ her workspace, for instance institute/ faculty storage, (cloud) storage such as laptop/ pc, OneDrive, Research Drive, VRE, etc. during the research project. The FDH enables the researcher to ‘publish’ data stored in the workspace at any point in time, generally this will be after all data analyses at the end of the research study/ project and usually includes only processed and cleaned data leading to the research conclusions.

Start of journey.

Steps (see figure 3 on next page for corresponding workflow):

1. The researcher prepares a data package for ‘publication’ in his/ her workspace (not provided by the FDH), optional with assistance or advice from a data steward or other support. A data package to publish contains for example: processed (de-identified and cleaned) data, data descriptions (metadata) including syntax and dictionaries, a data licence including terms of use varying from standard generic to more custom-made specific terms, etc.
2. The researcher opens the FDH web page (e.g., datahub.uva.nl), logs in with his/ her UvA credentials, and deposits a data package for publication by using one of two options:
 - a. **‘ready for uploading’**. Preferred option, but only if the data package is not too big (< 10 GB). The FDH presents the project titles (and other identifiers) registered by the researcher in Research Management Services (RMS: rms.uva.nl). Next, the researcher selects the project that belongs to the data package to start the upload. If **no projects** are registered in RMS and therefore, can’t be shown in FDH, the researcher provides a project title. Finally, the researcher selects the data package to upload. The researcher can modify the name of the (compressed) folder containing the data package, but automatically a version number will be added to the name.

This option enables the FDH to serve as a ‘gateway’ for data packages to be published, which means that after the upload, the FDH saves the data package on ‘intermediate’ storage. This allows the data steward to manage and check (i.e., quality control) the data package for publication. However, the faculty/ research institute determines whether checks by data stewards and/or other support is part of the procedure.

- b. **‘ready for transferring’**. This option can be selected if a data package has been prepared on the storage solution of the faculty/ research institute (size often > 10 GB) or on a common cloud solution such as OneDrive, Research Drive, or VRE. The FDH presents the project titles (and other identifiers) registered by the researcher in Research Management Services (RMS: rms.uva.nl). Next, the researcher selects the project that belongs to the data package for publication. If **no projects** are registered in RMS and therefore, can’t be shown in FDH, the researcher provides a project title related to the data package. Finally, the researcher provides the name of the data package. This name with a version number will be given to the (compressed) folder containing the data package in the publication platform.

This option uses a direct interface between the workspace and the selected publication platform (data repository) for the transfer of the data package. This means that **no intermediate storage** is available for the data steward to check the data package. Therefore, checks should take place on the same storage system on which the data package has been prepared. However, the faculty/ research institute determines whether checks by data stewards and/or other support is part of the procedure.

Workflow:

Figure 3. (Meta)Data Publication via Upload or Transfer.

The upload/ transfer option triggers the following automations in the FDH:

- a. Ingesting relevant metadata from sources (if available) such as Research Management Services (RMS: rms.uva.nl) and storing them structurally in the FDH metadata repository. If metadata already exist for the project in the FDH, the latest version of the metadata will be presented to the researcher, which can be modified and saved as a new version.
- b. If **a check** of the data package is part of the procedure, labelling the data package as '**check before publishing**' and notifying the 'assigned' data steward. After FDH login, the data steward gets an overview (list) of the prepared data package(s) 'Check before Publishing' and can also view the related metadata template (see step 3).
- c. If **no check** of the data package is part of the procedure, labelling the data package as '**ready for publishing**'.

Note:

- I. Researchers of the UvA faculties make use of RMS to register research projects and related content concerning data management, data protection, and ethics (FNWI for now only for ethical concerns). These registrations contain research related metadata. One of the FDH goals is to connect RMS as source for metadata extraction. However, also other sources could be connected when feasible. For instance, extraction of metadata stored in data collection systems (e.g., measuring instruments) or logging systems such as an electronic lab notebook (ELN). Automatic extractions are preferred, but a second-best option could be through imports of standard data exchange formats such as JSON and XML files when sources are able to provide these files straightforwardly.
 - II. The faculty/ research institute determines the procedure for checking the data package before publishing. This could range from no checks at all, some basic automated checks if the structure of the data package allows this, but probably not available in the initial version of the FDH, to more extensive manual checks by the data steward.
3. After the choice to upload or transfer the data package, the researcher once more chooses one of two options:
 - a. Publishing both data package and metadata. Thereafter, the researcher selects the preferred publication platform for publishing the data package and metadata (will always be sent to Pure too and FDH/Pure will be updated with DOI from publication platform). In the beginning the choices will be the institutional data repository Figshare, or the external data repository DANS or Zenodo. Other external (discipline specific) repositories will be added in time.
 - b. Publishing the metadata only. The metadata will be published on Pure/ UvA-Dare? This means the prepared data package for publishing will be stored on the 'long-term' archive but not published on a publication platform.
 4. The FDH:
 - a. First, automatically checks the ingested and stored metadata. If **no metadata** can be ingested an empty template will appear in step 4b.
 - b. Second, shows the researcher the stored metadata in a template and conveys when crucial metadata for publishing are missing or invalid in the template for the in step 3. made choices.
 5. The researcher completes the required metadata depending on the preferred choice of publishing. Crucial is adding the appropriate license/ terms of use. This license determines whether the data package can become directly available for download on the publication platform or can only be shared in a certain way after an 'request for use' procedure. The researcher can request support from and communicates with data stewards at the faculty or metadata/ RDM specialists at the library using an integrated messaging/ mailing system to finalize the metadata. Only a minimal set of pre-defined metadata is required for publishing. Nonetheless, storing additional metadata is possible and further refinement of

these metadata can be done in time with the help of the faculties. The status ('ready'/ 'not ready') of the metadata for publishing in addition to archiving will be visible in the FDH for the researcher as well as the data steward.

6. If the faculty/ research institute guidelines:
 - a. **Don't instruct** manual checks (or automated checks have been resolved) and the **metadata is 'ready'** (see step 4), the FDH initiates automatic publication of the (meta)data to the selected platform. After the publication, the researcher and data steward and/or system administrator are notified of the (meta)data publication. This event could trigger the (automatic) removal (after a predefined period) of the data package from the intermediate storage of the FDH or the faculty/ cloud storage solution on which the data package has been prepared.
 - b. **Do instruct** manual checks, the data steward checks the data package on the FDH (intermediate storage) or the faculty/ cloud storage solution on which the data package has been prepared. For instance, whether the data package is suitable for publication and matches the guidelines. Therefore, the data steward must be authorised to access the FDH storage or the faculty/ cloud storage to do the check. The data steward can interact with the researcher and/or other support by means of the integrated messaging system in the FDH to provide or receive support/ advice to complete the data package for publishing.
7. If the data steward considers the data package:
 - a. As **'not ready'**, the researcher accesses the workspace (i.e., the system on which the data package has been prepared) to rework the data package for publishing. Possibly in collaboration, but then collaborators (i.e., data steward, other support) should be authorized to access and edit the data package on the workspace. Thereafter, the researcher uploads the 'reworked' version to the FDH or in case of 'transferring' the data package directly, marks it as 'updated', requesting the data steward for another check.
 - b. As **'ready'**, the data steward labels the data package as **'ready for publishing'** in the FDH. Next, if also the **metadata is 'ready'** (see step 4), the data package will be published automatically and accordingly to the selected publication platform either from the FDH intermediate storage or from the faculty/ cloud storage solution. The data package's status in the FDH changes to **'published'**. After the publication, the researcher and data steward and/or system administrator are notified of the (meta)data publication. This event could trigger the (automatic) removal of the data package (after a predefined period) from the intermediate storage of the FDH or the faculty/ cloud storage solution on which the data package has been prepared.

End of journey.

Note:

- I. The data package associated with the publication whether or not selected to publish on a publication platform is at all time stored in the 'long-term' archive.

Journey 3: Data Re-Use

In short:

The FDH besides data archiving and publishing including metadata management, will support data re-use. First this will be limited to researchers who themselves deposited data packages (and are responsible for these packages) stored in the Data Archive via FDH. These researchers will be provided the option in the FDH to download or transfer a copy of their data package from the archive to their workspace. Over time the alignment of the FDH with a RDX solution (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8269272>) will extend and optimize the process of making data available for re-use inside and outside the UvA. The optimal steps could be the following.

Steps:

1. Researchers can search for UvA datasets (archived or published) to re-use in two ways:
 - a. In the UvA (only if you have access to the FDH) by searching the metadata repository in the FDH enabling associated datasets to become available directly (downloadable from the archive or via link from publication platform) or after a request, review, and approval procedure supported by RDX depending on the specified permissions for UvA researchers, institutes, or faculties.
 - b. Outside the UvA, potentially worldwide based on metadata published on publicly available publication platforms or through PURE and therefore included in publicly available and searchable metadata catalogues such as UvA-DARE. If data packages are published as open data, they will be immediately available for download. Otherwise, they can be made available after a request, review, and approval procedure supported by RDX depending on the associated license (terms of use).
2. The researcher of the UvA can re-use data from the archive:
 - a. Directly when he/she meets the right criteria (e.g., the data were collected by this researcher and are from an ongoing project, etc.). Subsequently, the data package can be automatically transferred to the researcher's workspace or can become downloadable.
 - b. After request when he/she does not meet the right criteria. In this case, the request is submitted to higher management of the associated research institute for review and approval.
3. The researcher outside of the UvA can re-use data (the researcher has become aware of the existing UvA data through published related metadata):
 - a. Directly when data packages have been published as 'open access'. The data package can be downloaded from the publication platform.
 - b. After a request, in the beginning likely by using an email link published on the publication platform, later with the help of a RDX platform. Depending on the criteria for re-use, one of the following options may be issued:
 - i. Data packages not openly available (taken from the archive, figshare or external data repository) or a selection (prepared and checked on compliancy by researcher and/or data steward) can be downloaded after complying to the terms of use (license) and/or signed agreements (e.g., joint controller agreement, processing agreement, duty of care provision, etc.).
 - ii. Data packages not openly available (taken from the archive, figshare or external data repository) or a selection (prepared and checked on compliancy by researcher and/or data steward) can be made available in a trusted research environment (TRE: zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.4594703; surf.nl/secure-environment) after complying to the terms of use (license) and/or signed agreements.
 - iii. Data packages can't be re-used directly, but it is possible to send a data analysis script which can be executed within an UvA workspace set-up by the data steward with support of ICTS and/or faculty. The analysis results can be received after a compliance check by the data steward and after complying to the terms of use (licence) and/or signed agreements.
4. Researcher(s) and data steward(s) have access to a dashboard in FDH, in which information related to data re-use can be found, for instance the number of downloads/transfers, complied (i.e. signed) terms of use/ agreements, uploaded analysis scripts, etc.